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ABOUT CATERING SERVICES OF STUDENTS

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Abstract: Some features of catering services of students are studied. Defects of the organization of the qualitative and quantitative parties of food are revealed at a considerable part of students that can reduce the adaptation potential and operability of an organism, to form premorbid and pathological conditions of an organism.

Keywords: catering services, students, macronutrients, micronutrients

ОСОБЕННОСТИ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ПИТАНИЯ СТУДЕНТОВ

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Аннотация: Изучены некоторые особенности организации питания студентов. Установлены недостатки в организации качественной и количественной сторон питания, что может снижать адаптационный потенциал и работоспособность организма, вызывать нарушения обмена веществ, преморбидные и патологические состояния организма.

Ключевые слова: организация питания, студенты, макроэлементы, микроэлементы

Relevance. Food as the most important factor of the environment is capable to have various impact on a human body, including at the correct organization, to provide the high level of health, high performance and active longevity [1-4]. Food determines duration and quality of human life. Mistakes in structure of food become one of the reasons of much serious illness, including most widespread cardiovascular diseases and cancer. Hygienic actions for prevention of alimentary and dependent diseases are based on modern knowledge of essence of processes of a metabolism and maintenance of a homeostasis. In this connection, the research of all aspects of catering services of various social groups, including, student's youth is relevant. A number of factors, including a way of life and behavior of students, can significantly influence qualitative and, especially, quantitative parties of food. There are numerous data on disturbances in catering services of students. Student is youth – one of the most valuable categories of society for which maintenance of health the organization of the healthy (rational) nutrition is necessary [5-8].

Purpose. Studying of some features of catering services of student's youth was defined by the purpose of the sociological research conducted by us.

Materials and methods of a research. In work, methods of comparative analysis and sociological survey, which was conducted in the winter of 2020 among students 3 courses of medico-psychological faculty, are used (57 people at the age of 19-21 years). The obtained data are processed statistically.

Results of a research. The balanced diet is food of the healthy person directed to prevention of alimentary, cardiovascular, gastrointestinal, allergic and other diseases. The balanced diet provides constancy of internal environment of an organism (homeostasis) and vital needs (growth, development, working capacity, activity of various bodies and systems) at the level corresponding to working conditions and life. The organization of a balanced diet of students is complicated by economic factors (in the having many children, incomplete and lost one parent families), complexity of ensuring enrollment of products and non-optimal processing of food. The general requirements to a diet are formulated in the following main postulates:

1) the daily food allowance has to correspond on energy value to organism energy expenditure. Energy value of a diet of student's youth has to correspond to 2000-2400 kcal (at the expense of proteins of 260-290 kcal, at the expense of fats of 630-730 kcal, at the expense of carbohydrates of 1100-1400 kcal, i.e. an optimum ratio P:F:C = 1:2,5:4,8);

2) physiological requirements of an organism have to be provided with the main substances in quantities and proportions which have a maximum of useful effect. The food allowance of students has to contain about 70 g of protein, 80 g of

fats and 260-360 carbohydrates. The ratio between them in an age group of 18-29 years on weight will be 1:1,1:4,9;

3) the chemical structure of food has to correspond to the fermental alimentary systems of an organism as much as possible. Any disturbance of compliance of chemical structure of food to fermental konstellyation leads to frustration of a metabolism and forming of various morbid conditions;

4) the diet has to be correctly distributed during the day. Meal 4 times a day. By the first option for the first breakfast 25 % of energy value of a diet, are the share of the second breakfast of 20 %, for lunch of 35 % and for a dinner of 20 %. By the second option for breakfast of 25 %, for lunch of 35 %, for an afternoon snack of 15 % and for a dinner of 25 %;

5) the balanced diet has to be faultless in the sanitary and epidemiologic relation. Products in food of students should not constitute health hazards because of existence of physical, chemical or biological contaminants or processes of damage at the wrong storage and realization.

The analysis of assessment of food showed that 77.6 % of respondents are familiar with bases of the organization of a balanced diet, but only 28.9 % of respondents consider the food correct. Limit themselves in food of 38.4 % of respondents. Most of students noted «health – it is important, but it is not always possible to take care of it». Basic reasons that interfere properly to eat are lack of time during the day, the way of life and a lack of appliances.

As a result of studying and the analysis of the obtained data it is established that a part of respondents (36.8 %) have not breakfast at all and only 2 times a day eat food, 43.2 % – 3 times; 10.5 % – 4 times; 6.7 % – 5 times; 2.8 % – 1 time. From 27.3 % interviewed only adhere to a diet, and 72.7 % eat at different times day and the main meal at them falls on evening. Students know about harm of a dense dinner and lack of a breakfast enough, but often neglect it for various reasons. Small amounts of students of 15.7 % have breakfast in the canteen of the university, and 36.8 % have dinner.

In this regard, it is necessary to include an offal, bread from coarse flour in a diet, fruit, and fresh greens. For ensuring high performance of the visual analyzer the amount of vitamin A, which contains in liver, eggs, butter, carrots has to be increased). The deficiency of mineral substances can cause development of serious diseases: deterioration in work of immunity; diseases of skin, nails, hair; allergy; diabetes and obesity; idiopathic hypertension; blood pathologies; scoliosis, osteochondrosis, osteoporosis and many others.

For prevention of diseases, it is necessary to use more vegetables and fruit (to the 700-800th in day). Vegetables and fruit suppliers of «live» vitamins, microelements, and sources of complex carbohydrates. Vegetables and fruit contain a lot of cellulose and is low-calorie that gives feeling of satiety. Therefore, they can be eaten in any quantity and not to be afraid of excess body weight. In

addition, cellulose as if the adhesive tape, collects harmful chemicals and carcinogens and brings them out of an organism. In vegetable food, there are pectins, which help to bring harmful cholesterol out of an organism. Fruit and vegetables contain antioxidants, which protect organism cells, preventing oxidation of organic compounds. Vegetables and fruit improving work of bodies and systems, including a brain, promote maintaining clarity of mind and memory. It is established that insufficient amount of fruit in a food allowance have 91.2 % of students, vegetables – 47.3 %, bread and grain products – 73.5 %, excess of sweets (candies and chocolate) – 47.4 % of students. Feedstuffs or nutrients are a part of products. The organism uses them for updating and creation of cells and fabrics, for obtaining energy, for coordination of biochemical and physiological functions.

Conclusion. The received results demonstrate about the students who are available for a considerable part shortcomings of the organization of the qualitative and quantitative parties of food what can reduce the adaptation potential and operability of an organism, to cause disbolism, premorbidal and morbid conditions of an organism.

Thus, based on the analysis of data of sociological poll it is possible to draw a conclusion that food of students has disturbance in qualitative and quantitative aspects and needs correction and improvement.

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